

PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS OF SIMULTANEOUS
INTERPRETATION OF UNESCO TEXTS

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Abstract: In this article, issues of United Nations texts are discussed and several solutions as well as recommendations are made.

Key words: United Nations, translation, UNTERM, translators.

The task of translation at the United Nations is highly demanding due to various factors. Translators need to meet the highest standards of accuracy, readability, and use of appropriate terminology while managing heavy workloads and tight deadlines. The documents they translate encompass a wide range of topics, including technical, political, scientific, social, economic, and legal matters. These documents also vary significantly in length and can be related to anything from peace and security to statistics, international law, economic development, and the right to food.

Moreover, the role of multilingual documentation in supporting multilateralism and Member States' discussions means that translation deadlines are consistently tight. The workload is unpredictable, with new agenda items or international crises leading to sudden rushes of urgent translation tasks. Additionally, translators need to write in a neutral style of their language, with a focus on ensuring that their translations are understood across all regions where that language is spoken.

United Nations translators are supported by technological tools such as multilingual terminology databases and translation memories, which assist in maintaining consistency and accuracy in their work. The translations produced by UN translators not only aid the Organization's operations but also serve as critical records of its activities.

Furthermore, aside from translating texts, language staff in the translation services also review and edit documents in their respective languages to ensure clarity, coherence, and factual accuracy. They also contribute to the standardization of terms across the six official languages and play a role in developing official United Nations terminology and the multilingual database UNTERM, which is publicly available. The translation environment at the United Nations is characterized by its intensity and high reliance on advanced technology.

Translating at the United Nations is an intricate and demanding task owing to various factors. The process involves ensuring the highest quality standards in terms of accuracy, readability, and usage of correct terminology, all while meeting stringent workload standards and translation deadlines to guarantee prompt delivery. The translated documents encompass an extensive spectrum of technical, political, scientific, social, economic, and legal subjects, ranging from peace and security to statistics, the law of the sea, economic development, and the right to food. Moreover, these documents can differ significantly in length, from extensive 60,000-word reports to concise 1-page diplomatic notes. Meeting the crucial role of multilingual documentation in supporting multilateralism and Member States' deliberations inevitably results in tight processing deadlines. Moreover, the workload can be highly unpredictable, as new agenda items or international crises can generate sudden rushes of urgent translation tasks.

Another challenge arises from the necessity for translators to write in a neutral variant of their language, ensuring that the translations are readily understood across all regions where the language is spoken. This involves maintaining a consistent style of language that is accessible to all speakers of the given language. In addition, because United Nations documents often form part of a series, consistent terminology use becomes essential in many cases. United Nations translators are aided significantly by automated reference-checking and term-matching features of the technological tools they employ, including multilingual terminology databases and translation memories. Such tools support the translators in achieving accurate and consistent translations, critical for the organization's operations.

The translators at the United Nations not only facilitate the work of the organization but also play a vital role in documenting its activities, serving an essential informational and archival function. Furthermore, beyond translation tasks, language staff in the UN translation services also undertake document editing to ensure clarity, coherence, and factual accuracy before translating them into other languages. Members of the English Translation and Editorial Service also produce the official summary records of certain meeting bodies. Moreover, a key responsibility of translators is the standardization of terms in the six official languages. All translation services contribute to the development of official United Nations terminology and the multilingual database UNTERM. This database is made available to the public. Translation at the United Nations is not merely a linguistic pursuit; it is an intense, high-tech

endeavor requiring rigorous attention to detail and an unwavering commitment to accuracy and precision in navigating the complexities of multilingual communication. The United Nations translators work in an entirely electronic setting and make use of cutting-edge technological tools like eLUNA, the in-house computer-assisted translation tool, bitext alignment tools, the United Nations terminology database (UNTERM), and document repositories such as the Official Document System (ODS). These tools help to maintain the consistency and accuracy of their translations. Additionally, they utilize online dictionaries, glossaries, and in-house databases, and when necessary, conduct research or consult with fellow translators, *précis*-writers, and relevant experts.

The translation process at the United Nations demands a high level of intellectual engagement. Translators must deeply comprehend the meaning of the documents they are translating to accurately convey all the nuances into the other language. This includes dealing with intentionally obscure or ambiguous wording in diplomatic communications, requiring superior linguistic and analytical skills.

Collaboration and teamwork are essential among United Nations translators. They work together, share assignments and knowledge, and consult with one another to address any translation or terminology issues that may arise. Furthermore, translators and editors actively gather and verify new or outdated terms, consulting with in-house specialists, language professionals, and outside sources, including technical experts and specialized websites. Verified terms are then stored in the multilingual database UNTERM, directly accessible through the eLUNA translation tool. Regarding the necessary skills, United Nations translators are expected to have a flawless command of their primary language and an excellent knowledge of, in most cases, two other official languages. They are also required to write in a clear and grammatically precise style in their main language. Additionally, they need to be adept at conducting research using both United Nations and external sources and stay informed about developments in the subjects dealt with by the United Nations. Intellectual curiosity, willingness to master new subjects, and superior linguistic skills are critical for this role.

To meet the high quality standards expected of United Nations documents, translators must thoroughly understand the subject and nature of the document being translated, ensuring accuracy, completeness, and consistency, and adhere to the style and usage rules of their translation service. The work of United

Nations translators offers a unique opportunity to gain insight into world affairs and international diplomacy, work on diverse and high-profile texts, and become experts in specific subject areas.

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